

Surfactants free synthesis of superparamagnetic magnetite (Fe₃O₄) nanoparticles : Spectroscopic, magnetic and AFM studies

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Abstract : Superparamagnetic Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles with diameter of ~7 nm were prepared by a colloidal method, without employing surfactants and using precursors like FeCl₃·6H₂O, FeSO₄·7H₂O, deionized water and using NH₄OH solution (29% vol.) as precipitating agent. The synthesized product was characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), scanning electron microscopy attached with energy dispersive X-ray (SEM-EDS), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) surface area, thermogravimetric analysis (TGA-DTG), and atomic force microscopy (AFM). The hysteresis loops of the magnetite nanoparticles were measured using a superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID) and the results showed a superparamagnetic behavior at room temperature.

Keywords : Magnetite nanoparticles, colloidal method, superparamagnetic, TEM, AFM, SQUID.

Introduction

Magnetite (Fe₃O₄) nanoparticles have been of immense scientific and technological interests because of their unique magnetic, optical and electric properties^{1,2}. The wide applications of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles include high density information storage³, ferrofluid technology⁴, electronic devices⁵ and catalysis⁶. Recently, Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles have attracted great attention for many important tissue engineering and biomedical applications, such as cancer therapy, drug delivery, theragnostic applications, hyperthermia, manipulation of proteins and cells, MRI and magnetic separations⁷, due to their non-toxicity, high chemical stability and biocompatibility in nature^{8,9}.

Seeking the importance, several procedures including sol-gel method¹⁰, hydrothermal synthesis¹¹, reverse micelles method¹², co-precipitation¹³ and thermal decomposition route¹⁴ have been developed for the preparation of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles. The above reported procedures suffered from various drawbacks as the synthesis process is complicated, requires relatively high temperature and the percentage yield is very poor. However, co-precipitation method has been extensively employed at atmospheric

conditions using toxic surfactants. The use of such surfactants may pose toxic effects in the organism and on the environment. Herein, we presented a simple co-precipitation method to synthesize the superparamagnetic Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles with relatively high yield.

Results and discussion

The TEM image for Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles is shown in Fig. 1(a). Most Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles exhibit spherical shape and have a particle size range from 5 to 15 nm (Fig. 1(b)). The BET surface area of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles was 87 m² g⁻¹. The value obtained comparable to that of value reported by Yean *et al.*¹⁵.

SEM image shows that the Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles are nearly spherical and the corresponding EDS spectrum (Fig. 2) confirm the particles are composed of Fe and O, without any impurity; the C peak is from the double-sided carbon tape used in the sample preparation.

The XRD pattern of the prepared Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles compared with JCPDS reference pattern of magnetite (No. 19-0629) are shown in Fig. 3. Six characteristic peaks for Fe₃O₄ (2θ = 30.1, 35.5, 43.1, 53.4, 57.0, and 62.6°)

Fig. 1. TEM image of magnetite nanoparticles (a) and size histogram of suspension (magnetite was dispersed in hexane) of magnetic nanoparticles obtained from DLS measurements (b).

Fig. 2. SEM image of magnetite (a) and EDS spectra of magnetite (b).

Fig. 3. XRD spectra of magnetite nanoparticles.

and the position (35.5°) of the most intense line in the XRD pattern are shown. The mean particle size calculated from Fe_3O_4 diffraction peaks according to the Debye-Scherrer equation was 7 nm, which is in good agreement with the result observed by TEM shown in Fig. 1. No peak of the other component except Fe_3O_4 has been detected in this sample. The XRD pattern of the prepared Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles agrees well with JCPDS reference pattern (No. 19-0629) of Fe_3O_4 ^{16,17}.

The pH of zero point charge (pH_{pzc}) was determined by measuring the zeta potentials for Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles at varied pH. pH_{pzc} indicates the electrical neutrality of the adsorbent and surface at a particular value of pH. The pH_{pzc} of Fe_3O_4 was 6.2 (Fig. S1), which is close to that reported in literature¹⁷.

The FTIR spectra of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles depicted in Fig. 4 provide valuable information regarding the nanomaterial structure. The spectrum of the Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles exhibits strong peaks at 585 cm⁻¹ is due Fe-O functional group corroborates that the main phase of prepared nanoparticles is Fe₃O₄¹⁸ and at 998 and 1086 cm⁻¹ was due to the C-O stretching. The band at 1402 cm⁻¹ was most likely due to CH₂ scissoring. The band at 1600 cm⁻¹ was due to H-O-H bending vibrations of adsorbed water. The presence of C-O and CH₂ groups comes from the ethanol and ultra pure water adsorbed during the washing of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles.

Fig. 4. FTIR spectra of magnetite nanoparticles.

Magnetic measurements of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles were investigated with a vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) at room temperature in the applied magnetic field sweeping from -50 to +50 kOe and it shows the superparamagnetic behavior (Fig. S2a). It is reported in literature that magnetic nanoparticles with size < 30 nm with zero coercivity and zero remanence exhibits superparamagnetism¹⁹. Magnetic saturation value of the Fe₃O₄ was 84 emu/g. Such an excellent magnetic property means that the prepared Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles have strong magnetic responsivity and can be separated easily from the aqueous solution with the help of an external magnetic force. The ZFC curve exhibits a maximum blocking temperature at 55 K which is indicative of highly magnetic nature of the synthesized Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles (Fig. S2b). The FC curves show a temperature independent behavior on moving to lower temperatures, indicating the presence of a magnetic ordered state with high

anisotropy²⁰.

Fig. 5 shows the TGA curve for the Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles, which indicating a three stage for total weight loss (33%) in temperature ranges 25–200, 200–430 and 430–550 °C. The first slight amount of weight loss corresponded to the evaporation of adsorbed water molecules. The second step represents the significant weight loss could be attributed to the removal of C-O and CH₂ from the surface of Fe₃O₄. The third step is dedicated to the evaluation of thermal degradation due to phase transfer through the reduction of magnetite to maghemite or wustite²¹. The DTG curves of the Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles are shown in Fig. 5. Two DTG peaks representing weight loss appeared at ~75 °C and at 330 °C and were associated with the endothermic nature. There is also a third exothermic peak at ~480 °C on the DTG curve at which temperature phase transition occurred²².

Fig. 5. TGA-DTG curve for the Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles.

AFM image of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles adhesion on mica surface are shown in Fig. 6. The scanned surface area was 2 × 2 μm, and the Z scale range was in the range of 35 nm to 2 μm, adjusted according to the height of the detected nanoparticles or aggregates. The size of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles (~8.28 nm) was confirmed by measuring the height of attached nanoparticles on mica surface, with the scanned area being reduced in order to increase resolution. Most of the scanned nanoparticles were in the spheroidal shape. This particle size is remarkably close to the size range, 5 to 15 nm, determined by the photon correlation spectroscopy. No significant nanoparticles agglomeration was observed for Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles and as can be seen in Fig. 6 the particles have good size distribution.

Fig. 6. AFM image of magnetite nanoparticles (a), 3D image of magnetite nanoparticles (b) and histogram of magnetite nanoparticles (c).

Fig. S1. Graph showing the zeta potential of Fe₃O₄ magnetic nanoparticles.

further purification. FeCl₃·6H₂O, FeSO₄·7H₂O and NH₄OH were purchased from British Drug House, Poole, England. The highest purity analytical reagent grade NaOH, HCl, NaCl and acetone were supplied by E. Merck, Mumbai, India.

Synthesis and characterization of magnetic nanoparticles :

Fe₃O₄ magnetic nanoparticles were synthesized using method of Peng *et al.*²³ with some modifications. 6.1 g of FeCl₃·6H₂O was dissolved in 100 mL of distilled water followed by addition of few drops of concentrated HCl in order to prevent precipitation of iron as Fe(OH)₃, thereafter, 4.2 g of FeSO₄·7H₂O was dissolved and the mixture was heated at 90 °C, then 10 mL of NH₄OH (29%) was added rapidly. The mixture was stirred at 90 °C for 30

Fig. S2. (a) VSM magnetization curve of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles and (b) ZFC and FC measurements of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles.

Materials and methods :

Chemicals and reagents :

All of the reagents were of analytical grade with the mass fraction purity of 0.99 and used as received without

min and then cooled to room temperature. The black substance was collected by centrifugation at 10000 rpm and washed to neutral with ultra pure water. The obtained black precipitate was Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles.

FTIR spectra of the Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles were recorded with a spectrophotometer (ABB Canada Model : FTLA-2000) in the range 400–4000 cm⁻¹, using a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ and 32 scans to determine the surface functional groups. The spectra of the dried samples were obtained in KBr pellets (Merck, spectroscopic grade) containing 1 wt% of magnetic nanoparticles. SEM studies were carried out using a scanning electron microscope (Scanning Electron Microscope-Zeiss EVO40) at an electron acceleration voltage of 20 kV. The surface area was determined with Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) surface area analyzer using a computer controlled automated porosimeter (Micromeritics ASAP 2020, surface area analyzer), by means of adsorption-desorption of ultra pure nitrogen at 77 K. TEM images of the magnetic nanoparticles were obtained with a Transmission Electron Microscope, Philips (Model : CM200) operating at an accelerating voltage of 200 kV. TEM samples were prepared by placing a drop of the suspensions on a copper grid with a carbon membrane film. The crystalline structures of the samples were identified from X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns recorded in the 2θ range 20–80° with a scan step of 0.05° (2θ) for 5 s on a Philips X'pert Pro diffractometer using CuKα radiation (λ = 1.54060 Å). The system includes the ultra-fast X'Celerator detector PW3015/20 and a secondary monochromator. The crystalline size was determined from the diffraction peak using the Scherrer method. The zeta potential of magnetic nanoparticles was measured at various pH with a Zeta Probe, Colloidal Dynamics, USA. The particle size in aqueous suspensions was measured using a Mastersizer 2000 laser particle size analyzer (Malvern, UK). Solution pH was measured using a pH/Ion meter (pH meter 335, Systronics, Ahmedabad, India). The magnetic properties of the dried magnetic nanoparticles were studied using a commercial Quantum Design superconducting quantum interference device (S600, SQUID magnetometer Cryogenic Ltd.) and with a vibrating sample magnetometer (Oxford VSM). The hysteresis loops were run at 300 K for a maximum applied magnetic field of 50 kOe. Temperature-dependent zero-field-cooled (ZFC) and field-cooled (FC) magnetization measurements were obtained for a range of temperatures between 0 and 380 K with an applied magnetic field of 50 Oe. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA-DTG) was carried out with a thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA 209 F3 NETZSCH, Germany). The samples were ~ 10 mg and

the measurement was carried out under nitrogen atmosphere. Dynamic runs were carried out from 30 to 800 °C at the heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ and isothermal runs were carried at 400 °C. AFM images were recorded with a Scanning Probe Microscope (NT-MDT NTEGRA, Russia). The magnetite nano powder were dispersed in ethanol and ultra sonicated for 15 min at room temperature. Thereafter, the dispersed liquid was mounted on a mica surface (1 cm × 1 cm). The tapping mode was selected for scanning the sample. In tapping mode, the cantilever is driven to oscillate up and down at near its resonance frequency by a small piezoelectric element mounted in the AFM tip holder so that the tip interacts very briefly with the sample. Tapping mode AFM is ideal for imaging soft materials that can be easily scratched and modified. The tip was single beam etched, tapping mode etched silicon probes, and using NOVA software, section analysis of images was conducted to measure the size of particles or their aggregates. For each experimental condition, three mica sheets were prepared and at least three images were obtained for each mica-sheet sample.

Conclusions

In summary, we have developed a facile route to prepare highly performance Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles using a modified colloidal process. This fabrication approach has several advantages compared to other synthesis methods. Only iron rich low cost precursors, FeCl₃·6H₂O and FeSO₄·7H₂O, were used in the presence of NH₄OH as precipitating agent and no surfactants are required, which made this process easy to scale-up for mass production. The relatively higher reaction temperature of this system favors the materials with a higher crystallinity, consequently, higher magnetization. Finally, the size distribution of the nanoparticles is much narrower than those particles produced from traditional methods. Therefore, this approach offers a facile route to replace the traditional methods for the preparation of superparamagnetic water-dispersible Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles and is expected to be applicable in various biomedical and environmental applications.

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